

ZOONYMS AS DERIVATIONAL MEANS FOR DESCRIBING HUMAN APPEARANCE AND BEHAVIOR IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The article examines the use of zoonyms as derivational means for describing human appearance and behavior in English and Uzbek. It highlights the semantic role of metaphors, particularly zoonym-based ones, as productive tools in expressing complex personal traits vividly and figuratively. Drawing on examples from both languages, the study categorizes zoonym metaphors into two groups: those describing physical appearance and those describing character traits. According to comparative analysis, many metaphors coincide cross-linguistically. Metaphorical zoonyms not only enrich descriptive language but also reflect cultural values and symbolic associations unique to each language community.

Introduction. There are semantically derived means of describing human qualities, and they are one of the productive tools of descriptive language. Figures of speech can be examples for semantical derivational means of describing human trait, as they have fully or partially derived meaning.

Especially metaphors play a crucial role in the English and Uzbek language, particularly in describing human appearance and character. They allow speakers to express complex ideas vividly and concisely while adding nuance and emotional color to communication. Their function in English will be explored and compared to Uzbek metaphors.

Additionally, metaphor, as a fundamental cognitive and linguistic tool, enables speakers to conceptualize abstract traits by linking them to concrete experiences. In describing human appearance and character, metaphors often rely on associations with animals, nature, objects, and mythology.

Discussion and results. Zoonyms are one of the most common ways of describing both human appearance and character in both languages.

Table 1. Zoonym metaphors for describing human appearance

English language	What quality does it describe	Uzbek language
lion	someone who appears strong and courageous, often with a	sher , arslon

	commanding presence.	
snake	someone with a slender or agile physique.	Suv ilon
snake	someone with poisonous, unfriendly look	ilon
owl	someone with large, expressive eyes	ukki
fox	someone with sharp features or a cunning look	tulki
bull	someone with a thick, muscular neck, implying strength and robustness.	buqa
Cat	someone who moves elegantly and smoothly, suggesting agility and poise.	kiyik

This table shows that English and Uzbek languages are not completely different from each other in use of zoonym to describe human appearance. In most cases, metaphors are fully matched with each other (i.e. fox-tulki). There is one distinction is found in describing someone who moves elegantly and smoothly. In Uzbek culture this kind of people are not seen as cat, because cat is not considered as graceful. “Kiyik” and its movements are thought to be appropriate for elegant women.

Table 2. Zoonym metaphors for describing human character:

English language	What quality does it describe	Uzbek language
snake	someone who is deceitful or treacherous, hiding their true intentions.	ilon
wasp	someone who speaks poisonous, hurting words	ilon
fox	someone who is clever	tulki

	and shrewd, often using their intelligence to outsmart others.	
dove	someone with gentle, soft features, conveying peace and serenity.	musicha
bee	busy person	asalari, chumoli
chicken	someone who is cowardly or easily frightened.	quyon
bear	someone who sleeps deeply	ayiq
rat, judas goat	someone who betrays easily	echki
ox	someone who is considered dull	tovuq, qo'y
bull	someone who speaks to others without respect and tries to fight with them	it

In metaphors that are used for describing human personality have more differences than human appearance when they are compared between two languages, and there is an essential role of cultural concepts. For example, dove is considered as a symbol of peace in Uzbek language too as in English, but the word “musicha” is frequently related with adjectives “gentle, harmless and soft.” The Uzbek expression “musichayi beozor” (harmless small bird”) can be a good example.

Another variety is seen in connecting coward features of people with animals. In English the expression “chicken-hearted” is used, while Uzbeks use “quyonyurak” for people who are frightened easily.

But still most zoonym metaphors of describing human character are similar in both languages (deceitful people are snakes, people who sleeps deeply are bears).

Conclusion. Zoonyms are used to express human traits and outer look in a more expressive and imaginative way. These linguistic devices offer insight into cultural values and cognitive patterns, reinforcing shared understandings within a speech community. Understanding and mastering these expressions is

essential for achieving fluency and appreciating the deeper layers of communication.

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